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Такташева Д.Р.Филиал РГУ нефти и газа (НИУ) имени
И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте, старший преподаватель**ПРОБЛЕМЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ЦИФРОВЫХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ СТУДЕНТОВ
НЕФТЕГАЗОВОГО УНИВЕРСИТЕТА** <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7466131>**АННОТАЦИЯ**

Актуальность темы данной статьи обусловлена влиянием цифровой экономики на формирование набора ключевых компетенций и подготовку востребованных специалистов в современном мире. В статье рассмотрены наиболее распространенные подходы к структуре модели компетенций работников, востребованных в Индустрии 4.0, включающих цифровые компетенции. Кроме того, в статье анализируется практический опыт формирования цифровых компетенций студентов Филиала Российского государственного университета нефти и газа (НИУ) имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте, на основании которого разработаны предложения по совершенствованию формирования цифровых компетенций студентов нефтегазового вуза.

Ключевые слова: цифровизация, цифровая экономика, цифровые компетенции, нефтегазовая отрасль, цифровые технологии, симулятор буровых работ.

Taktasheva D.R.Branch of Russian state university of oil and gas (NRU)
named after I.M. Gubkin in Tashkent, senior lecturer**ISSUES OF DEVELOPING DIGITAL COMPETENCES OF STUDENTS OF OIL AND
GAS UNIVERSITY****ABSTRACT**

The urgency of the topic of this article is justified by the impact of the digital economy on the development of a set of key competences and educating the specialists in demand. The article considers the most common approaches to the structure of the competence model of employees working in Industry 4.0, including digital competencies. In addition, the article analyzes practical experience of developing digital competencies of students of the Branch of the Russian State University of Oil and Gas (NRU) named after I.M. Gubkin in Tashkent and on the basis of the research results the author has worked out relevant proposals to improve the formation of digital competences of students of the oil and gas university.

Key words: digitalization, digital economy, digital competences, oil and gas industry, digital technologies, drilling simulator.

Taktasheva D. R.

I.M. Gubkin nomidagi (MTU) Rossiya davlat neft va gaz universiteti
Toshkent shahridagi filiali, katta o'qituvchi**NEFT VA GAZ UNIVERSITETI TALABALARINING RAQAMLI VAKOLATLARINI
SHAKLLANTIRISH MUAMMOLARI****ANNOTATSIYA**

Ushbu maqola mavzusining dolzarbligi raqamli iqtisodiyotning zamonaviy dunyoda asosiy vakolatlar to'plamini shakllantirish va talab qilinadigan mutaxassislarni tayyorlashga ta'siri bilan bog'liq. Maqolada 4.0 sanoatida talab qilinadigan, shu jumladan raqamli kompetentsiyalarni o'z ichiga olgan xodimlarning vakolatlari modeli tuzilishiga eng keng tarqalgan yondashuvlar muhokama qilinadi. Bundan tashqari, maqolada I. M. Gubkin nomidagi Rossiya davlat neft va gaz universiteti (MTU) filiali talabalarining raqamli vakolatlarini shakllantirishning amaliy tajribasi tahlil qilinadi. Toshkent shahrida neft-gaz universiteti talabalarining raqamli kompetentsiyalarini shakllantirishni takomillashtirish bo'yicha takliflar ishlab chiqildi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamlashtirish, raqamli iqtisodiyot, raqamli vakolatlar, neft va gaz sanoati, raqamli texnologiyalar, burg'ulash simulyatori.

Introduction. Current oil and gas business requires permanent changes to be implemented by oil and gas companies. A new factor is rapidly developing that makes an impact on the vector of development of the oil and gas business, making critical amendments in its processes. This factor is caused by the trend of digital transformation of the economy. In this regard, currently the education must adapt to the requirements of the time and constructively use the advantages of digital evolution. Heads of various companies, top managers, representatives of corporate universities, personnel management services, university rectors, education experts and the advanced pedagogical community are engaged in an active dialogue about which models of digital competencies should be implemented into practice. Nowadays the educational environment focuses on such aspects as competence models for the digital economy within the framework of lifelong learning, the new role of the class instructor in teaching digital skills, innovation-based models of education and advanced pedagogical technologies, optimal balance of digital, professional and soft skills. Therefore, the urgency of the “digital competencies” term is obvious, which means it is important to comprehend the terminology of concepts related to digital transformation. This is necessary for a comprehensive view of digital skills and the benefits of digitalization towards the development of the oil and gas business workforce. Thus it is impossible to develop approaches to the development of digital competencies (DC), working out of models for the DC development, the technique for the research, as well as the strategies for the formation and updating of the DC.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev repeatedly noted in his speeches, one of the primary objectives of the consistent socio-economic development of Uzbekistan is the widespread introduction of ICT and digital technologies. This is precisely the area that represents an efficient tool that can ensure high-quality reform of economic sectors and spheres of public life. Digital transformation is one of the basic trends in the development of the states at the current level, changing the framework of almost all spheres of the economy and the social sphere. The COVID-19 pandemic has affected many sectors of the economy, but has contributed to the accelerated development of the IT industry. In addition, it has demonstrated importance of introducing information, communication and digital technologies into the performance of public authorities, private enterprises, and public organizations.

Currently the government of Uzbekistan pays particular attention to strengthening cooperation with foreign countries, in particular, in the area of introducing innovations and advanced technologies. In terms of this issue it is impossible to ignore the role and experience of the countries of the East, which demonstrate impressive GDP growth rates. Such participants in the region as China, India, Vietnam today act as the locomotive of the world economy. Japan and South Korea retain leadership in many areas of innovative and high-tech industries. Singapore, Malaysia and

Thailand show exceptional achievements in the export of goods and services to world markets. And the United Arab Emirates, Qatar, Saudi Arabia are making serious progress in the field of alternative energy, innovative projects in the field of finance and space exploration.

Analysis. In Uzbekistan development of the oil and gas industry is inextricably linked with the introduction of innovations, and at all its stages. Nowadays oil industry is the locomotive of digitalization and introduction of innovations. In this regard a proper assessment of the concepts associated with digitalization, including in education, will consistently ensure the flexibility of the concept of the formation of the DC, provides a dynamic character to the development and updating of digital skills, which will definitely result in the increased employment opportunities and improvement of productivity.

The phenomenon of digitalization has made certain amendments in the educational process of higher education. Increasingly, we use words and phrases: digitalization, digital electronic environment, digital competencies, digital skills, digital literacy, digital content, digital footprint, digital twin, digital shadow, etc.

The term “digitalization” originally implies the transfer of analog information into digital. Now digitalization in a broad sense is perceived as social and economic transformations occurring under the influence of information technologies and the corresponding transformation of business models. The ongoing digitalization and the prospects for its deepening and expansion raise questions about changing not only the organization of education, but also the very psychology of attitude towards it.

It should be noted that interest in the digitalization trend is explained by its wide potential for economic development. According to preliminary estimates of the McKinsey Global Institute, in China, up to 22% increase in GDP by 2025 may occur due to Internet technologies. In the US, the expected value added by digital technologies by 2025 could be 1.6-2.2 trillion USD.

The term “digital literacy” appeared at the end of XX century and gained popularity in 1997 in the book “Digital literacy” by P. Gilster (Gilster, 1997). The term “digital literacy” has been studied in numerous research papers by foreign researchers, such as Gilster, Martin, Madigan, Ilomäki, Kantosalo, Lakkala. For example, according to P. Gilster, “Digital literacy is the ability to critically understand and use information received through a computer in various formats from a wide range of sources”. Following the idea of P. Gilster, A. Martin, concretizing this definition, understands digital literacy as the awareness, attitudes and ability of individuals to properly use digital tools and means for identifying, accessing, managing and integrating, evaluating, analyzing and synthesizing digital resources; building systems of new knowledge, as well as communicating with other people for the purpose of constructive social actions in the context of specific life situations [10].

Chetty K., Wenwei L., Josie J., Shenglin B., pointing out the dynamism of the concept of digital skills and the lack of generally accepted approaches, recommended five dimensions, namely: information literacy, computer literacy, media literacy, communication literacy, technological literacy. According to the researchers, each dimension is further influenced by three aspects: cognitive, technical and ethical. These five dimensions and three aspects, according to the researchers, in a broad sense should underlie the conceptual definition, measurement and teaching of digital literacy. However, a person can have a high level of digital literacy, but at the same time a low level of education. Therefore, knowledge-intensive industries need, among other things, specialists who can work with big data, competently extract data and interpret the results of big data analysis [5].

Foreign scholars Liisa Ilomäki, Anna Kantosalo, Minna Lakkala rightly believe that the concept of digital competence is an emerging concept and is associated with the development of technology, and also depends on political goals and expectations regarding citizenship in the knowledge society. It consists of many skills and competences, and its coverage spans several areas: media and communications, technology and computing, literacy and computer science. Authentically, digital competence consists of 1) technical skills in the use of digital technologies; 2) the ability to use digital technologies in a meaningful way for work, study and for everyday life in general in various activities; 3) the ability to critically evaluate digital technologies; 4) motivation to participate

in digital culture. Digital competence is considered as a basic foundation in policy documents; however, studies have not yet formed a standardized, generally accepted concept [9].

K. Ala-Mutka, Y. Punie, C. Redecker substantiated key competencies a little earlier [4]. In line with their ideas, the European Union (2010) has created a core competency framework for lifelong learning in the knowledge society, which outlines eight core competencies. These include: 1) communication in the native language; 2) communication in foreign languages; 3) mathematical competence and basic competences in the field of science and technology; 4) digital competence; 5) learning to learn; 6) social and civic competencies; 7) a sense of initiative and enterprise; 8) cultural awareness and self-expression. Thus, although the concept of the formation of digital competence is not sufficiently theoretically substantiated, nevertheless, digital competence is one of the 8 key competencies. The development of the concept of digital competence has been concentrated in the field of authentic concepts and in the field of skills related to technologies, including digital ones.

According to Soldatova G.U., digital competence is the ability of an individual based on the constant mastery of knowledge, skills, motivation, responsibility to critically, effectively, safely choose and apply digital technologies in different areas of life [2, p. 152]. Soldatova G.U. identifies four types of digital competence: 1) information and media competence: knowledge, skills, motivation and responsibility associated with the search, understanding, organization, archiving of digital information, its critical reflection and the creation of materials using digital resources (text, visual, audio and video); 2) communicative competence: knowledge, skills, motivation and responsibility necessary for online communication in various forms (e-mail, chats, blogs, forums, social networks, etc.); 3) technical competence: knowledge, skills, motivation and responsibility to effectively and safely use a computer and related software to solve various problems; 4) consumer competence: knowledge, skills, motivation and responsibility that allow using a computer to solve various everyday tasks that involve meeting various needs [2, p.153].

The universities majoring in oil and gas cannot but respond to the challenges of digital transformation. Digitalization requires new, completely different competencies, different from those possessed by university graduates. Moreover, according to Tulchinsky G.L., the digital competence of university graduates should exceed the existing range of competencies [3, p. 126].

As far as we know, in Uzbekistan development of the oil and gas industry is interconnected with the introduction of innovations and advanced technologies. Nowadays oil industry is the locomotive of digitalization and introduction of innovations. Modern industrial mining facilities are so complex that it is almost impossible to work here without digital technologies, automatic control, modeling, advanced equipment, modernization and re-equipment. Starting from the use of digital technologies in geophysics and seismic exploration, to drilling oil and gas wells, automation of oil and gas production processes, pipeline management, transport infrastructure, not to mention the accounting of manufactured products, exports, foreign exchange and tax revenues from the industry - all this is impossible to achieve without digitalization, high energy efficiency and capital-labor ratio. Today the latest digital technologies help companies achieve a high level of efficiency: smart fields, digital twins of refineries are leaders in the implementation of digital innovations, which is the main element of competitiveness in general. And therefore it is very essential that the students of an engineering university, in particular, the university majoring in oil and gas, study professional software products, which constitute the basis for operating automated workplaces of industry engineers.

In his Message to the Oliy Majlis, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev has emphasized that the time has come for an in-depth study of geology and this fact imposes the Branch with a big responsibility of comprehensive study of geological disciplines. In connection with its implementation the Branch of Russian State University of Oil and Gas (National Research University) named after I.M. Gubkin in Tashkent has launched the Innovation Center for Research. Equipped with more than 30 latest sophisticated computers and workstations, the scientific platform enables to combine investigations of all areas of the oil and gas business, conduct both laboratory and practical classes, as well as applied research. They include carrying out geological and geophysical studies, data interpretation, three-dimensional modeling, hydrodynamic modeling, calculation and

justification of risks, analysis and processing of statistical data, large data sets, fulfilling industry orders.

In addition, drilling simulators are widely used to train highly qualified and in-demand specialists in the industry.

Effective training of drilling machine operators is of crucial significance in optimizing productivity, improving safety and minimizing operating costs. Technical errors made in the drilling cycle results in a significant increase in costs at all subsequent stages of production and processing. Based on this, simulators of drilling rigs for operations are widely used in the educational process to provide training, retraining and certification of drilling machine operators in conditions of open pit mining.

The operator of the open pit drilling rig simulator observes the virtual environment on three high-resolution widescreen projection displays located directly around the rig operator's cab, allowing for efficient travel and drilling operations. The cab of the drilling rig is reproduced with high accuracy, all instruments and controls for drilling and movement are correctly located around the driver's workplace.

An example of using the simulator "Drilling rig operator":

- a student (trainee), moving around the location and following the navigator pointer on the right, needs to approach the desired object (the place or object is indicated by a jumping green vertical arrow);

- upon reaching the object, a trainee must press the "use" button, after which the object will be located in the info-space;

- when hovering the cursor over a segment of the object under study, it will be highlighted in yellow and when you click the left mouse button, a panel with information about the segment will appear on the screen;

- the user needs to complete all tasks according to the given conditions, i.e. perform drilling operations advance drilling to avoid damage to equipment.

During the learning cycle of moving and drilling, the rig operator performs all the actions that are performed in real equipment. Models of drilling rigs move and turn realistically, and the exact dynamics of the behavior of the drilling module, interaction with rocks of given characteristics (hardness and drillability) provide a drilling experience that clearly demonstrates the safety and productivity of work.

At the Branch of the Russian State University of Oil and Gas (NRU) named after I.M. Gubkin in Tashkent we have made an experiment among students of 3-4 courses of the "Oil and Gas Business" faculty. This experiment is aimed at assessing the performance of students divided into two groups. During the study process of the first group of students, particular attention has been allocated to the development of their digital competencies based on the use of advanced cutting-edge teaching aids, and the study process of students of the second group was implemented in a traditional way. As the experiment has demonstrated, the performance of students of an oil and gas university, who have used innovative digital learning tools in their learning process, have been higher than the performance of students who have been trained in the traditional way, without the use of digital technologies (Table 1):

Table 1

Comparative analysis of student performance indicators in the educational process using digital technologies and in the traditional educational process (Developed by the author based on the conducted research.)

Indicators	Student performance indicators using digital technologies (max 100 points)			Performance indicators of students studying the traditional method at the end
	Before using digital technologies	Upon completion of the course using digital technologies	Change, in %	

				of the course (max 100 points)
Latest 3D Oil and Gas Field Modeling Software	68	82	+ 14%	76
Drilling Simulator	62	84	+ 22%	71
Use of IT technologies	74	85	+11%	80
Smart panels	71	83	+12%	80

As it is obvious from the results of the experiment, efficient formation of digital skills of students, in addition to developing their general professional competencies that will be necessary in their future professional activities, can make a favorable impact on their overall academic performance.

Conclusion. The digitalization of the economy and education involves universities in the active discussions on how to quickly and constructively respond to the challenges of the digital economy. One of the key participants in the movement towards the digital economy is a university graduate prepared to work with information and digital technologies. Possessing core digital competencies becomes a factor in the demand for a university graduate in the current labor market. The need to develop approaches in the formation and development of the DC of graduates of oil and gas universities requires reflection, justification, research, building models of digital competencies in the areas of training, designing tools to support and update available digital competences. Definitely, efficient application of digital competences of the graduate of the oil and gas university in their future career will promote successful development of the oil and gas industry of our country, as well as the national economy as a whole.

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